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CONSENT FORM

Adopting LLM-based software development tools: a software practitioners perspective

Introduction

This study is conducted to gain an in-depth understanding of current industrial perspective on software practitioners adopting Large Language Model-based tools on software development tasks.

The research is approved by the Human Ethics Committee of Monash University, Australia for five years on <date>. Reference Number: 44875.

Confidentiality

This survey is anonymous. Any research publication published as a result of the study will not identify you, your company or any non-participant in your company.

Storage of data

Storage of data Data in a Google Drive with restricted access (only investigators have access) for a period of 5 years and destroyed thereafter.

Further information about this research is available at [Explanatory Statement](#).

Complaints

Should you have any concerns or complaints about the conduct of the project, you are welcome to contact the Executive Officer, Monash University Human Research Ethics Committee (MUHREC):

Executive Officer

Monash University Human Research Ethics Committee (MUHREC)

Room 111, Chancellery Building D,

26 Sports Walk, Clayton Campus

Research Office

Monash University VIC 3800

Tel: +61 3 9905 2052 Email: muhrec@monash.edu Fax: +61 3 9905 3831

INVESTIGATORS

Prof. Rashina Hoda (Chief Investigator), Prof. John Grundy, Assoc Prof. Christoph Treude, and Mr. Samuel Ferino.

CONTACT INFORMATION

If you have any questions regarding this interview and the project, feel free to contact Mr. Samuel Ferino, Prof. Rashina Hoda, or Prof. John Grundy at {samuellucas.demouraferino, rashina.hoda, john.grundy}@monash.edu.

CONSENT

I confirm that I have understood the nature of the research, and I have had the opportunity to ask questions and have had them answered to my satisfaction.

- I agree to take part in this study
- all information collected from me will be kept confidential to the research team and I will not be identified in publications arising from the study.

- I understand that I am free to withdraw my participation at any time, and to withdraw any data traceable to me up to 30 days from the date of the participation without giving a reason
- I understand some personal information (e.g., age range, gender) may be collected for anonymous reporting
- I understand that I will be audio-recorded during the interview
- I understand that interview recordings will be uploaded to a secure commercial server (i.e., Otter.ai or Nvivo) for transcription
- I give consent to share the collected from me with other researchers on this project who are included in the ethics approval

OPTIONAL

- I wish to receive the summary of findings of the study
- I wish to have my interview transcript returned to me and have the opportunity to edit the transcript for 30 days from the receipt of the transcript

NOTE

We assure details of the participants, and all other confidential information shared will be kept confidential. The names and details of the participants will not be specified in any of the publications or reports.

Full Name (First name and Last name):

Email Address:

Signature:

× **SIGN HERE**

[clear](#)

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Demographics

This section is intended to gather basic information of the participants.

NOTE

We assure details of the participants, and all other confidential information shared will

be kept confidential. The names and details of the participants will not be specified in any of the publications or report.

Please, provide your **LinkedIn** account or any other **professional social account** that you use.

How old are you?

To which gender identify do you most identify?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary / gender diverse
- My gender identity isn't listed. I identify as:

- Prefer not to say

In which country do you currently reside?

What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- High School graduate, diploma or the equivalent and some college credit, no degree
- Trade/technical/vocational training
- Associate or Professional degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctorate degree
- Other
- Prefer not to say

What is your current professional role or job title?

- Software engineer
- Software developer
- Web developer
- DevOps engineer
- Cloud engineer
- Frontend developer
- Backend developer
- Mobile developer
- Other
-
- Prefer not to say

How do you describe your level of experience as a software developer?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="radio"/> Novice | <input type="radio"/> Highly experienced |
| <input type="radio"/> Advance beginner | <input type="radio"/> Other |
| <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> <input type="text"/> |
| <input type="radio"/> Intermediate | <input type="radio"/> Prefer not say |
| <input type="radio"/> Experienced | |

In what area/domain do you primarily work

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="radio"/> Information Technology | <input type="radio"/> Telecommunications |
| <input type="radio"/> Finance | <input type="radio"/> Gaming |
| <input type="radio"/> Manufacturing | <input type="radio"/> Other |
| <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> <input type="text"/> |
| <input type="radio"/> Government | <input type="radio"/> Prefer not say |
| <input type="radio"/> Healthcare | |

How many years of professional experience in software development do you have?

- Less than 1 year
- 1 to 2 years
- 3 to 5 years

- 6 to 10 years
- More than 10 years
- Prefer not to say

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Large Language Model-based tools experience

This section is intended to gather information regarding your experience using LLM-based tools.

How long have you been using Large Language Model (LLM) - based tools **in general**?

How long have you been using Large Language Model (LLM) - based tools for **software development-based tasks**?

Which Large Language Model-based tools have you used (if any) at work? e.g.

OpenAI ChatGPT; GitHub Copilot

What development tasks do you usually seek help from LLM-based tools?

- Requirement-related tasks (e.g., requirement identification)
- Code-related tasks (e.g., coding, debugging)
- Test-related tasks (e.g., test case development)
- User-related tasks (e.g., user documentation)
- Other
- Prefer not say

What is your approximate number of prompts per day?

Considering your experience using LLM-based tools, rate how much you agree with the sentences below: **(please select answers to all items)**:

Strongly disagree

Strongly agree

I fear artificial intelligence

I trust artificial intelligence

Artificial intelligence will destroy humankind

Artificial intelligence will benefit humankind

Artificial intelligence will cause many job losses

Does your organisation have a policy regarding usage of LLM-based tools?

- Yes, there is a policy and it support the usage
- Yes, there is a policy and it doesn't support the usage
- No, there is no policy
- I do not know
- Prefer not say

Is there anything else you want to share about your perception involving usage of LLM-based tools or our study in general?

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